

This is the hybridised absolute paradox, and it goes as followed: If it is simply detailed, it is therefore specifically complex, however, if it is specifically complex, it is therefore simply detailed. And so the outcome of that paradox is that it is specifically complex. However, if it is specifically complex, it is therefore simply detailed, however, if it is simply detailed, it is therefore specifically complex. And so the outcome of that paradox is that it is simply detailed. And so the outcome of that absolute paradox is that it is either specifically complex or simply detailed.

This set is timed as 22:17, and is dated as the 9th day, of the 2nd month, of the 2025th year.